

Short communication

RAINIERIA CALCEATA (DIPTERA: MICROPEZIDAE: TAENIAPTERINAE): A NEW SUBFAMILY, GENUS AND SPECIES TO GREECE

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Micropezidae is a small family of slender flies, with 22 species in Europe belonging to 5 genera (Oosterbroek, 2006). *Rainieria* Rondani, 1843 is a small genus with four species in the Palaearctic (Kurina, 2004). Two species occur in Europe, *R. calceata* (Fallen, 1820) and *R. latifrons* (Loew, 1870) (Kurina, 2004; Ozerov, 2013).

***Rainieria calceata* (Fallen, 1820) (Fig.1)**

Greece, Thessalia, Nomos Larrisas, Mt. Olimbos (Olympus), Palia Sicaminia, N 40.006294, E 22.383984, 1200 m a.s.l., 26.07.2020, leg. G. Kakiopoulos, det. S. Alexiou, 1 ♀. The specimen is deposited in the collection of Entomon Lab (ENTL). Our specimen was collected after it entered a stationary car through an open window.

Rainieria belongs to subfamily Taeniapterinae, so far unknown from Greece. Characters that separate taeniapterids from the other subfamilies are the arrangement of the setae on the head as well as the male genitalia (Papp & Schumann, 2000). The larvae of *Rainieria* depend on old forests of deciduous trees, on the rotting wood of which they feed (Oosterbroek, 2006). The adults can be found in a variety of habitats.

Rainieria calceata can be separated from the closely related *R. latifrons* by the coloration of the femora and markings of the wings (van der Weele, 1998). The former is not uncommon in Europe while the latter is widely spread in the Palaearctic but very rare in Europe, being recorded mainly from Central-Eastern Europe (Kurina, 2004; Ozerov, 2013).

Figure 1. *Rainieria calceata*, Greece, Mt. Olimbos, female, lateral view (scale bar: 1 mm).

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НОВА ПОТФАМИЛИЈА, РОД И ВРСТА ЗА ФАУНУ ГРЧКЕ**

СОТИРИС АЛЕКСИУ И ЈОРГОС КАКИОПУЛОС

Извод

Врста *Rainieria calceata* је регистрована 2020. године и представља нови налаз за фауну Грчке. Такође, род *Rainieria* и потфамилија Taeniapterinae су први пут забележени у Грчкој.

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